

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 A Locus Number ① 16/I/80

Progress of Excavation With trowel and brush, removed ①
AT N wall revealed Hard packed gravelly ^{grey sand} ①a - dry crust over
①b hard packed gravelly ^{light} tan sand. This in turn overlaps ②
as shown in cut present before our clearance (see plan)
② here phasing out in slight "finger" of deposit. ② Greyish
sand (comes up brown when damp) w/ limestone frags, and ③
loose clean sand, considered mod in 1st removal in R16 to N
Balk. Evidence: Mod. paper etc. inclusions. But important to be
sure ③ is not ancient. If ancient, lower excavation line →

Locus Description LOOSE ^{SLIGHTLY} GREY FINE SAND ON SURFACE

Location in Square Across R16 A to wall

Under Locus SURFACE Over Locus ①a ①b ② ③ ③b

Locus Dimensions 2-4 cm depth

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

disturbing 4-4d would indicate ancient excavation - robbing later filled w/ clean sand, in turn disturbed by previous modern excavations.